

Control Dynamic Modelling for Electrodermal Activity Short-Term Responses

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Abstract

The concept of Electrodermal Activity (EDA) has been set as a concise measure that reflects the output of an integrated affective and motivational phenomenon that can occur within the central nervous systems of a person's body. The process is also known to be a valuable mechanism in studying behavioural medical concepts as a biomarker for an individual mind and traits. It can be set as a characteristic for subtle emotional responsiveness as part of the index that directs the examination of stress-interrelated effects on body functioning. Most research focuses on its response output concept and produces continuous sequential readings of the participants' nervous states, which is one of the most important attributes of the EDA measure. This paper tries to study its mechanism and methods of data generation by looking at the control dynamics that constitute the process of data generation and response readings in real time through simulation and model design based on a dynamic control system. Phasic changes were compared for each step in response output. The result shows that amplitude response scenarios are based on a time limit, and the reaction rate can be synchronous to a user activity based on a constant time interval for each data generation. A control physiological system can also be modified and emulated based on this concept.

Keywords: Electrodermal Activity, Dynamic control system, Magnitude response, Amplitude response, Synchronous user activity, Reaction rate

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1 Introduction

Integrating the concept of control dynamics and electrodermal activity (EDA) can be described as a measure of the neural-mediated cause of sweat from the sweat gland permeability as observed changes in the skin due to the electrical current between different parts of the skin.

This usually happens when a person is involved in an induced cognitive load that involves a lot of mental activity [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6]. The signals in EDA reflect the action of the sympathetic nervous systems from the eccrine glands of the body. It is mostly known as the galvanic response from variations of the electrical conductance

of the response in the skin caused by the sweat secreted in a continuous response to stimuli [7, 8, 9, 10, 11].

It is possible to model the concept in EDA through the use of dynamic control systems starting with the initial stage of collecting data by applying a low non-invasive process of constant voltage to the skin and measuring the skin conductance [12, 13, 14, 15]. This process can be carried out by using an EDA biometric tool that measures the electrical changes and signals recorded by the inbuilt electrodes applied to the skin. The EDA is also linked to the inner regulation of internal temperatures [16, 17, 18] and research has shown that repeated strong associations with this signal can interpret the cognitive level of a person. The measure of the cognitive level is produced by the sympathetic nervous system that leads to changes in the Skin conductance response of a person. The signals in EDA can be reflected as the intensity of the emotional state which is known as emotional arousal, the level of emotional arousal changes in response to the environment i.e EDA can also be subject to environmental constraints like a distraction that can be an anomaly in an EDA reading which should not be overlooked. Positive and negative stimuli can also result in an increase in the arousal state of a person and also an increase in their conductance level. The EDA signal can be termed as not representative of the types of emotional states if it reflects the increase in arousal state to both positive and negative stimuli [19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25]. This is the main reason why dynamic controls are applied when studying the concepts in EDA signal propagation to show the intensity of arousal states that classify an amplitude response to either positive or negative stimuli.

2 Literature Review

Research has shown that EDA or skin conductance is not under conscious control, but it is rather a modulated autonomous sympathetic activity that drives the human behaviour aspect and also the cognitive and emotional response [26, 27, 28, 29, 30]. It offers direct insights into the autonomous regulation of the emotional state of a person. Some use it as an additional source of insights to validate self-reports, such as in surveys and interviews of participants during an experimental study. The concept works by detecting the changes in the ionic activity that result from changes in the sweat gland and the electrodes are more adaptive and sensitive to these changes that transmit the information to the bio device. The electrodes have an AG/AGCI (silver-chloride) with a contact point for the skin; they are mostly used for safe human contact and response readings and the application of dynamic control systems to its core concept can accurately help in transmitting the signal from the ionic activity with less error.

The most important parameters to consider during

the application of the dynamic control systems are the EDA phasic changes and Tonic changes (Figure 1). These parameters can help differentiate an increase in amplitude towards a reaction to both positive and negative stimuli. In EDA measurement, the time course of the signal propagation is considered to be the result of two different additive processes, such as the tonic base driver that fluctuates between seconds to minutes and the phasic component that fluctuates between milliseconds and seconds. Both changes in phasic activity and tonic activity can be identified in the sequential data stream or readings; there is a steep inclination to a significant peak and a slight and slow decline that correlates to the baseline level of the EDA signal [31, 32].

Researchers in EDA processes and phenomena normally focus on the latency and amplitude of the phasic changes based on the stimulus (sounds, images, and videos) onset. A significant change in EDA refers to an Event-related Skin conductance response (ERSCR) and this can provide information about the cognitive and emotional response of a person to a stimulus. An important event in EDA activity not related to the stimulus presentation is termed the Non-Stimulus-Locked skin conductance response (NS-SCR) [33, 34]. It is also possible to include quantitative data in an experimental study of emotional arousal by using the SCR values as several EDA peaks. This would lead to novel findings that uncover certain aspects of human behaviour analysis. An integration of such findings can be represented more easily using the dynamic control model that identifies and predicts response peaks through the magnitude and peak response of the EDA signal.

3 Method

The concepts used here are intended to present integrated system dynamics modelling conceptions and techniques to physiological response signals like the EDA signal propagation focusing mainly on the phasic and tonic changes of a given response using short-term time intervals. The dynamic control system methodology is mostly applicable to modelling convoluted systems at a physical level of an interdependent factor like the one presented in [35, 36], which investigates work in General Electric and radar systems. They termed a system dynamics as a grouping of parts that work together for a conjoint purpose. The electrodes in the EDA sensor are immersed with electric changes and magnetic fields that flux on the skin surfaces thereby generating a physiological relay from the skin to the output signal that is seen as physiological readings of the human emotional response. These controls can be integrated with the Dynamic control model and operate hierarchically with information and knowledge controlled by the classification of the response parameters. One of the purposes of the paper is to solve operational and strategic planning of relaying

Figure 1: The components that represent EDA response readings.

physiological signals in a way that one can be able to differentiate a tonic and phasic response to both positive and negative stimuli. An integrated system dynamics of the EDA sensor model can contain causal loops that can identify the feedback for the interaction between a user and the stimulus of the system. These loops can contain peak reactions and baseline levels; this represents elements with possible capacities that change over time. Equation 1 represents the changes in response rate on input signal X to response signal y based on a third-order differential equation with external constant constraint A, B and C due to environmental factors with response to time t , demonstrating the reaction to basic external stimulus.

$$y - \frac{d^3 X}{dt^3} = -A \frac{d^2 X}{dt^2} + B \frac{dX}{dt} + C. \quad (1)$$

The baseline defines the rate at which peak response can change (Figure 2). The baseline effect is a critical component of the Physio-dynamic control model identifying its response change can contribute to the model building and response stratification. The closed chain of the EDA signal is a causal connection from the input signal through physical reaction in the skin surface dependent on the amount of cognitive load that produces the baseline effect on the readings. The feedback loop is formed as a chain where the amplitudes and peaks influence the baseline and recovery time of response and this in turn changes the rise in proceeding amplitudes. The peaks can also influence the recovery level which is determined through a series of intermediate supplementary parameters like the latency (delay) and magnitude of the response. The result section discusses some of the output of the phases of the Physio-dynamic control.

4 Result

The R packages of de-solve libraries solve the initial value problem in Equation 1 for the Physio-dynamic control model and the solver uses key required components of the system to implement the model equations as a function of response output. The initialized simulation time is set to constant and helps to create the simulation of the EDA response vector sequentially. Figure 3 shows the step response for the EDA response signal on a 318secs time interval for a short-term response with the error rate detected as $0.27\mu s$, this is close to an accurate response reading and a hundred percent exact similarity to an original reaction from a person.

Figure 4 shows the response reaction from four different components (Minimum EDA (Baseline), Current flow, Activity, and Reaction rate) in a single interaction with the external stimulus. The components have almost similar step sizes and response rates, showing the chronological order of the components. The baseline (MinEDA) has a similar and reverse effect in the model design (i.e. user activity should be regulated by the baseline response) and also the reaction rate (Equation 2). Resultant response y must be equivalent to the effect in the input signal X concerning time sequentially; this is also based on assumption.

$$y = y(Effect(X_y)x + Effect(X_{y+1})) \quad (2)$$

$$y_{n+1} = y(Effect(X_n)x + Effect(X_{n+1})) \quad (3)$$

The mind and skin are two separate entities in appearance, but they are two different sides of physiological reality. To measure sensation or physiological response

Figure 2: Dynamic control model for EDA physiological response.

Figure 3: Step-size response for EDA response signal.

about the magnitude of both physical and stimuli representation, a model is designed that expresses the theory of noticeable differences in the signal response. Figure 5 compares the step response of Magnitude, Anomalies, External Activity, and Event records for the simulation EDA response. Anomalies and Event when compared to its residual or integrated data input, the step response seems to diminish in error. The anomalies can be due to errors in measurement and signal switch which could re-

sult in large variations in data input. External activities or events are mostly due to distractions like hand claps or an unexpected loud noise that could distract the participants. These are also termed anomalies and are measured with the same unit. The residual input in dashed dark lines is synchronous but produces a lower step size than the one in external activities. This demonstrates the reduction of error in signal reception and current flow.

Figure 4: Step-size response for EDA response component.

Figure 5: Step-size response for EDA response component compared to the residual output.

Amplitude response was produced on difference scenarios (Figure 6), and this was run between 1 – 12%.

Amplitude response at 10% appears to have the largest error compared to other test sample data. To gradually

obtain the amplitude response, the absolute value of the data sequence is taken. To achieve this, the magnitude of the rational input is evaluated; the phase response is achieved by taking the integral of the numerator value and extracting its residual from the denominator value. This is done for each percentage scenario (Figure 6).

The amplitude signal response (Figure 7) can also be visualised in the increase and decrease of signal flow, where a particular currency can be selected to represent the baseline response. This amplitude response is also similar to the circuit response, and the behaviour of the EDA response. All phase reaction of the circuit depicts how the phase angle for complex signal frequencies can vary across different percentage frequencies. This is also a quantifiable range of signal between the highest and lowest signal readings. The resultant response reading can be similar to the real EDA signal response from a person.

5 Conclusion

The paper is aimed at demonstrating the basics of control dynamics of an EDA response reading by presenting a model that simulates the real-life scenario of EDA record. The paper looks at the mechanism and methods of data generation by observing the control dynamics that constitute the process of data generation and response readings in real-time through simulation and model design based on a dynamic control system. Phasic changes were compared for each step in response output. The result shows that amplitude response scenarios are based on a time limit, and the reaction rate can be synchronous to a user activity based on a constant time interval for each data generation. A control physiological system can also be modified and emulated based on this concept. The future perspective of the work is to demonstrate the idea behind the Physio-dynamic control by emulating the cognitive and emotional response of a person for user-robot interaction.

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Figure 6: Amplitude response of EDA on different scenarios.

Figure 7: Amplitude response of phasic changes based on time limit for an EDA signal reading .

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